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The Effect of the Al-Khawarizmi Education Model on Success in Electricity and Energy Saving in 4th Grade***Ecem SÖĞÜT¹, Mustafa YEŞİLYURT²**¹Amasya University, Department of Basic Education, Orcid: 0009-0009-4331-545²Amasya University, Faculty of Education, Orcid: 0000-0003-4108-7467**Abstract**

The purpose of this study is to investigate how the Harezmi Education Model affects students' performance when teaching "Electricity and Energy Conservation" in a fourth-grade science course. Two distinct fourth-grade classes from a rural school with a blended class system participated in the study. The study employed a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test–post-test control group.

Prior to the intervention, both groups were given a pre-test consisting of a textbook end-of-topic test, and it was determined that the students' initial knowledge levels were similar. The Khwarizmi Education Model was used to structure the educational process in the experimental group. Within this framework, students acted as "energy detectives," observing the school environment, examining electricity usage in classrooms, corridors, and different areas of the school, and identifying unnecessary energy consumption. They recorded their findings using an "energy reporting form" and shared them within the classroom.

In the subsequent stages of the process, students developed solutions to the problems they identified, prepared posters, created slogans, and established classroom rules for energy conservation. Collaborative learning and active participation were prioritized throughout this process. The traditional teaching method was applied to the control group.

The same achievement exam was given to both groups as a post-test at the conclusion of the intervention. The findings showed a significant increase in academic achievement in the experimental group where the Khwarizmi Education Model was applied. Only limited change was observed in the control group. The results indicate that the Khwarizmi Education Model is an effective approach to improving students' academic success.

Keywords: Science Education, Khwarizmi Education Model, Energy Conservation, Active Learning, Village School

* An oral presentation of this study was given at the 9th International Mediterranean Scientific Research Congress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Science is one of the fundamental subjects that supports students in relating scientific concepts to daily life, questioning the events they encounter around them, and thinking in a solution-oriented way. For science teaching to be effective at the primary school level, it is possible only if students not only listen to information but also use the information, make observations, discuss, and draw conclusions. Therefore, student-centered, inquiry-based, and teaching approaches that relate to daily life problems have an important place in science teaching.

The topic of electricity and energy conservation, included in the 4th grade Science curriculum, aims to help students become aware of the daily use of electrical energy, understand the importance of conscious use of energy resources, and develop conservation behaviors. However, when energy conservation is taught only through theoretical information, it can remain limited and abstract for students. Having students examine real-world electricity usage in the school environment, identify unnecessary consumption, and develop solutions can make learning more meaningful.

The Khwarizmi Education Model is a holistic educational approach that supports students in conducting research based on real-life problems, generating solutions, and developing products or proposals through collaborative work. The Khwarizmi Education Model supports students not only in acquiring academic knowledge but also in developing problem-solving, communication, collaboration, creative thinking, and responsibility skills.

In this study, the Khwarizmi Education Model was adapted to teach the topic of electricity and energy conservation in 4th-grade Science classes. Students in the experimental group acted as energy detectives, observing different areas of the school, identifying unnecessary electricity usage, filling out energy reporting forms, developing solutions, creating posters and slogans, and establishing classroom rules related to energy conservation. Thus, instead of learning the subject solely from textbooks, students connected it to real-life situations they encountered in school.

The main problem of the research is whether instruction based on the Khwarizmi Education Model increases the academic achievement of 4th-grade students in the subject of electricity and energy conservation. As a result, the study compared the experimental and control groups' achievement levels before and after the intervention.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Model

This research used a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test-post-test control group. The quasi-experimental design is a preferred model in research where groups cannot be assigned completely randomly in educational settings, but the effect of the experimental application can be examined comparatively (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2018; Creswell, 2012). In the research, instruction based on the Khwarizmi Education Model was applied in the experimental group, while the traditional teaching process was carried out in the control group in accordance with the existing program.

2.2. Study Group

The study group consisted of a total of 16 students studying in two different 4th-grade classes with a combined classroom structure in a village school. The experimental group included 8 students, and the control group included 8 students. Since the study group was a small sample, non-parametric statistical methods were used in the analysis of the data.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

In this study, an achievement test created using the end-of-topic test from the textbook was used to determine students' academic achievement on the subject of electricity and energy saving. The same achievement test was administered as a pre-test before the intervention and as a post-test after the intervention. The test consisted of questions designed to measure students' basic concepts related to the subject, their awareness of energy saving, and their inferences regarding daily life situations.

2.4. Implementation Process

During the implementation process, instruction in the experimental group was structured in accordance with the Khwarizmi Education Model. Students were involved in the process in the role of 'energy detectives' and were asked to examine electricity usage in the school environment. Students observed unnecessarily lit lights, electrical appliances left on, and situations that could lead to energy waste in classrooms, corridors, and different parts of the school.

Students recorded their findings using an energy reporting form. These forms included sections such as the observed area, the identified problem, the possible cause of the problem, and proposed solutions. Afterward, the students shared their findings in class and discussed possible solutions with their classmates.

In the continuation of the process, students prepared posters on energy saving, created slogans, and determined energy saving rules that could be applied in the classroom. During these activities, attention was paid to students working collaboratively, generating ideas, and making connections with daily life. Thus, the teaching process was conducted not only in the form of lectures, but also as an active learning environment that included observation, problem identification, solution development, and product creation processes.

In the control group, the topic of electricity and energy conservation was covered in accordance with the existing program, based on the textbook and teacher explanations. Students continued the learning process through the explanations, examples, and activities in the textbook. At the end of the intervention, the same achievement test was administered to both the experimental and control groups as a post-test.

2.5. Data Analysis

The data obtained in the study were analyzed using arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and Mann-Whitney U test. Descriptive statistics were calculated for the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and control groups. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine whether the difference between the groups was significant. This non-parametric test was preferred due to the small sample size. The significance level was accepted as 0.05.

3. FINDINGS

3.1. Findings Regarding Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 displays the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the experimental and control groups' pre-test and post-test success scores.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Regarding Pre-Test and Post-Test Success Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Pre-Test \bar{X}	Pre-Test SD	Post-Test \bar{X}	Post-Test SD	Mean Increase
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Experimental	8	75,12	8,83	95,50	6,00	20,38
Control	8	82,62	7,50	85.70	8,75	3,08

Table 1 shows that before the intervention, the pre-test arithmetic mean of the experimental group was 75.12 with a standard deviation of 8.83. The pre-test arithmetic mean of the control group was 82.62 with a standard deviation of 7.50. After the intervention, the arithmetic mean of the experimental group increased to 95.50, while the arithmetic mean of the control group was determined to be 85.70.

3.2. Mann-Whitney U Test Findings Regarding Pre-Test Scores

To ascertain whether the pre-test achievement levels of the experimental and control groups differed significantly, a Mann-Whitney U test was used. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Mann-Whitney U Test Results of Pre-Test Scores of Experimental and Control Group Students

Group	N	Rank	Mean Rank Sum	U	p
Experimental	8	6,81	54,50	18,50	0,112
Control	8	10,19	81,50		

Table 2 shows that the experimental group's mean pre-test rank was 6.81, while the control group's mean pre-test rank was 10.19. The pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups did not differ statistically significantly, according to the Mann-Whitney U test results (U=18.50; p=0.112; p>0.05). This finding suggests that prior to the intervention, there was no statistically significant difference in the groups' levels of success.

3.3. Mann-Whitney U Test Findings Regarding Final Test Scores

To find out if the experimental and control groups' post-intervention success levels differed significantly, a Mann-Whitney U test was used. Table 3 displays the findings.

Table 3. Mann-Whitney U Test Results of Final Test Scores of Experimental and Control Group Students

Group	N	Rank	Mean Sum	Rank	U	p
Experimental	8	10,88	87,00		13,00	0,028
Control	8	6,13	49,00			

According to Table 3, the experimental group's mean final test rank was 10.88, whereas the control group's mean final test rank was 6.13. The Mann-Whitney U test revealed a statistically significant difference in favor of the experimental group in terms of final test scores (U=13.00; p=0.028; p<0.05). This finding indicates that the teaching process based on the Khwarizmi Education Model is effective in improving students' academic achievement.

3.4. Observational Findings Regarding the Implementation Process

Students in the experimental group were shown to actively participate in the implementation process. Students, acting as energy detectives, examined different areas of the school, identified problems related to electricity usage, and developed solutions to these problems. During this

process, it was seen that the students did not remain merely in the position of listening to the teacher, but rather became active learners who observed, kept records, discussed, and developed suggestions.

The use of energy reporting forms helped students systematically record their observations. Poster and slogan projects allowed students to transform the information they learned into visual and verbal products. This helped students connect the topic of electricity and energy conservation with their daily lives.

In the control group, although students had learned basic information on the subject, the learning process progressed primarily through teacher explanations and textbook activities. Students in the experimental group showed more prominent behaviors in their explanations of the subject, such as providing examples from school life, identifying problems, and suggesting solutions.

4. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of the Khwarizmi Education Model on academic achievement in the subject of electricity and energy conservation in the 4th grade Science course. The pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups did not differ statistically significantly, according to the findings. This indicates that there was no significant difference in achievement levels between the groups before the intervention. However, post-test scores following the intervention showed a substantial change in favor of the experimental group. The increase in the post-test arithmetic mean of the experimental group to 95.50 and the p-value of 0.028 found in the Mann-Whitney U test result show that the Khwarizmi Education Model has a positive effect on academic achievement.

The research findings support the idea that student-centered and problem-based teaching approaches can be effective in science education. The Harezmi Education Model allows students to observe, collect data, generate solutions, and work collaboratively based on real-life problems. In this research, students' examination of electricity usage in the school environment, identification of unnecessary consumption, and development of suggestions for energy saving contributed to their ability to relate the subject to daily life.

In science classes, it is important that topics directly related to daily life, such as energy conservation, are not limited to theoretical knowledge alone. Students observing energy use in their own school environments and developing solutions can increase the retention and meaningfulness of learning. In this respect, the Harezmi Education Model can be considered an effective approach, especially for science subjects that have dimensions of values, awareness, and behavioral development.

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that teachers incorporate more activities based on the Khwarizmi Education Model into their Science lessons. Activities such as energy detective work, in-school observation, reporting forms, poster design, slogan creation, and classroom rules development can be implemented regarding electricity and energy conservation. These activities can support both students' academic achievement and their awareness of environmental responsibility and conservation.

The Khwarizmi Education Model can be explained by its structure that guides students to identify real-life problems, develop solutions collaboratively, and take an active role in the learning process (Yeşilyurt, 2021; Ministry of National Education, 2024). In problem-solving and active learning-based learning environments, students' ability to make sense of, apply, and discuss information instead of passively receiving it is considered among the important factors

supporting increased academic achievement (Jonassen, 2000; Prince, 2004).

The study has some limitations. It was conducted with a total of 16 students in a combined classroom setting in two village schools. Therefore, it is recommended that the findings be retested in different school types, at different grade levels, and with larger samples. Furthermore, future research could examine not only academic achievement but also students' energy-saving behaviors, environmental awareness, problem-solving skills, and collaborative work skills.

KAYNAKÇA

- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2018). *Eğitimde bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri*. Pegem Akademi.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *111*(23), 8410-8415.
- Jonassen, D. H. (2000). Toward a design theory of problem solving. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, *48*(4), 63-85.
- Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı. (2024). *Fen Bilimleri Dersi 4. sınıf 6. ünite: Enerji Dedektifleri*. Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli.
- Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, *93*(3), 223-231.
- Yeşilyurt, M. (2021). Meta-Analysis of the Effect of Technologies on Primary School. *Temel Eğitim*, *3*(2), 26-41. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/1678439>